

INTRODUCTION

The topic of the article is relevant because in an increasingly competitive environment companies must develop effective pricing strategies to attract and retain customers. Understanding the factors that influence pricing helps companies adapt to changes in the market.

Changes in the economic environment, such as inflation, currency fluctuations, and economic crises, directly affect pricing policies. Analyzing these factors allows companies to be more flexible in responding to changes.

Studying the factors influencing consumer perceptions of prices helps companies better understand their target audience and adapt their offerings to meet their expectations.

Advances in technology and the digitalization of business are opening up new opportunities for pricing, such as dynamic pricing and the use of big data to analyze consumer behavior.

With globalization, companies often face different pricing strategies in different markets. Understanding the factors affecting pricing in different countries becomes critical for successful international operations.

It should also be noted that consumer preferences in the Donetsk People's Republic (DPR) may differ from those of other regions, which requires a deep understanding of the local market. In the context of conflict and international isolation, companies in the DPR face unique challenges, such as limited access to resources and markets. This requires a specific approach to pricing and market entry strategy.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The materials of the study included articles from periodical peer-reviewed journals (Journal of Regulatory Economics, Journal of Economics, Journal of Consumer Policy, Review of Industrial Organization, Environmental Science and Pollution Research, International Economics and Economic Policy, Future Business Journal, etc.) and economic research on pricing policy and its factors.

Methods: quantitative analysis of statistical data to identify trends and patterns in the pricing policy of the DPR; SWOT analysis: assessment of strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats related to pricing policy in the DPR; modeling.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Pricing and pricing policies vary from industry to industry and depend on many factors. Pricing policy has a significant impact on product quality and consumer perception of the product.

T. B. Bjørner et al. analyzed the impact of switching from cost-of-service-based regulation to price cap-based regulation of drinking water quality in Denmark. The authors found that the change in regulation did not reduce the quality of drinking water in Denmark [1].

Z. Ghandour & O. R. Straume study the optimal design of a public financing scheme in a mixed oligopoly with one public supplier and two private suppliers competing with each other. The inclusion of one of the private suppliers in the public financing scheme eliminates the negative externality of competition between private suppliers, which, other things being equal, leads to inadequate quality assurance [2].

R. Chakraborti and G. Roberts hypothesize that the expectation of shortages caused by price regulation may motivate households to stock more and thereby exacerbate shortages caused by regulation. The authors prove this hypothesis: in regions where unexpected announcements about new regulations were made during the pandemic, the demand for a certain list of goods increased [3].

L. Grigsby-Duffy et al. wrote that price promotions introduced at supermarkets would encourage unhealthy eating behaviors, which led to the Australian government-approved restrictions. These interventions aim to support the promotion of healthy products, consumer education, etc. [4].

J. C. Arteaga and D. Flores study some aspects of fraud and price regulation in gasoline retailing. The authors show that competition, fraud penalties, and law enforcement efforts reduce fraud incentives regardless of the price regime. Price cap regulation creates additional fraud incentives and reduces welfare [5].

Pricing policies in the energy sector are crucial for both energy companies and consumers.

H. Xu et al. study the relationship between energy price fluctuations and economic level changes under different price control scenarios. The results show that energy price fluctuations have high conduction efficiency on the overall price index in the scenario without price control [6].

W. Roeger and P. J. J. Welfens write that significantly increased gas prices from summer 2022 – in the context of Russia's supply cuts to the EU – led to an abnormally high electricity price. Higher gas prices or reduced supply by Russia to the EU could lead to higher electricity prices, higher inflation, and lower real incomes. The authors propose subsidizing gas prices in the electricity market [7].

Pricing in the healthcare system is a complex and multilevel process involving many factors and participants. It has a significant impact on the availability of medical services, the quality of treatment, and the sustainability of the system as a whole. Factors affecting pricing are input costs, supply and demand, competition, and regulation.

S. Selvaraj et al. write that the Indian government is trying to keep prices under control through drug price control orders. The authors estimate that antibiotic sales immediately decreased after the intervention [8].

L. Z. Rand and A. S. Kesselheim write that since mid-August 2022, the US authorities have officially reduced the prices of the 10 most expensive prescription drugs covered by the Medicare state insurance program. According to the authors, the process of reaching the final price of a drug has three approaches: statutory discounts, maximum price setting, and arbitration between national (state) insurers and manufacturers [9].

J. Chen and M. Miraldo state that healthcare costs have continued to grow over the last twenty years. According to the authors, price transparency in hospitals has reduced the cost of laboratory and diagnostic tests, except for doctor visits. However, it has significantly increased the cost of healthcare services and prices in higher-rated facilities [10].

M. Shaikh et al. analyze the relationship between price regulation and the intensity of pharmaceutical research and development (R&D). According to the authors, the impact of price regulation is negatively related to R&D intensity. This is because price regulation is negatively related to cash flow and profit. Firm-specific effects explain the negative relationship between price regulation and R&D intensity [11].

Price regulation in the agricultural market is a complex process that involves many factors.

In many countries, governments use instruments such as minimum and maximum prices to stabilize the market [12]. For example, minimum purchase prices guarantee farmers income even if market prices fall.

States can also provide subsidies to producers to produce more when market prices are low [13]. This helps to sustain agriculture and prevents sharp price fluctuations.

Agricultural products are often seasonal in nature. For example, prices of fruits and vegetables can fluctuate dramatically depending on the time of year and the harvest [14].

More developed markets have their commodity exchanges where prices are formed based on actual transactions and expectations [15]. This also affects the price level in other regions.

Thus, each industry has its own characteristics that affect pricing and pricing policy. Each requires a unique approach that takes into account specific market conditions.

Many scientists have covered issues related to the formation of pricing policy in their works, but the problems of regulatory mechanisms that take into account the peculiarities of the region's economic development in the content of its pricing policy require a more in-depth study.

Analyzing the factors that determine the specifics of pricing policy (using the example of the DPR) requires a deep and systematic study of specific pricing conditions in an unstable economic and political situation. Collecting and analyzing data on consumer preferences, prices, and market conditions can be difficult in the context of conflict and economic instability. This creates challenges for scientific analysis and the development of informed recommendations.

The DPR has unique social, economic, and political factors that may interact with each other. We need to investigate how these factors affect pricing and how they may vary depending on external and internal conditions. Existing theoretical pricing models may not fully reflect the realities of the DPR market. This requires adapting or developing new models that take into account local conditions and peculiarities.

It is necessary to investigate how international sanctions, political isolation, and domestic economic conditions affect pricing policy. This includes analyzing the impact on supply and demand as well as on companies' strategic decisions.

Thus, the research problem is the need for a comprehensive analysis of the factors affecting pricing policy in the DPR in order to develop effective strategies that promote sustainable business development in an unstable environment.

The purpose of the article is: at the theoretical level – to substantiate the dialectical relationship between pricing policy and economic development of the region; at the methodological level – to determine the regulatory content of the pricing policy of the DPR.

RESULTS

Against the background of strategic changes and diversification processes that characterize the state of the economy of the DPR, the sphere of internal trade becomes one of the priority sectors of the economy. The development of the trade industry not only solves economic problems, acting as a source of increasing the population's incomes, but also realizes a social function, creating jobs for the segment of the unemployed who are people released from the coal industry, metallurgy, and engineering, which traditionally were basic for the Donetsk region.

In recent years, the Republic has seen positive trends in the sphere of trade, as evidenced by the growth of wholesale and retail turnover (see Table 1), the expansion of the networks of large trade enterprises, and the filling of the consumer market with goods from domestic producers.

Table 1

Dynamics of the growth of retail and wholesale turnover of trade enterprises

Indicator	2017	2018	2019	2020	Deviation, billion rubles		Growth rate, %	
					2019 to 2018	2020 to 2019	2019 to 2018	2020 to 2019
Volume of retail turnover, billion rubles	33.5	40.7	47.9	60.87	+7.0	+17.1%	+12.97	+31.2
Volume of wholesale turnover, billion rubles	53.5	61.0	64.0	71.59	+3.4	+5.6%	+7.59	+12.7

Source: [16, p. 51]

The positive dynamics of the number of retail trade objects attracts attention (see Figure 2). To stabilize the development of domestic trade and resume the work of empty facilities in the DPR, temporary administrators are introduced at retail facilities [17]. The main objectives of such an introduction are to ensure the development of infrastructure in the sphere of trade, saturation of the market with consumer goods, improving the quality of trade services and socio-economic indicators in the sphere of trade in general. The introduction of temporary administrators made it possible to ensure the resumption of trade facilities' work, increase budget deductions, increase turnover volume, and create more than 650 jobs. As of January 1, 2021, 13,366 retail trade facilities, 1,758 public catering facilities, and 3,453 consumer services objects were operating in the Republic.

Figure 1 Dynamics of changes in retail trade facilities in the Donetsk People's Republic
Compiled from the source [16]

Despite the fact that the trade industry is largely a self-regulating segment of the regional economy, the existing regulatory mechanisms in the consumer market cannot sufficiently ensure the compliance of the interests of trade entrepreneurship and consumers. Therefore, there is a need to strengthen state regulation in this area, the constitutive basis of which is the normative-legislative base and the system of executive controlling measures.

The results of the analysis of types and forms of regulatory impact of the state on the formation of pricing policy made it possible to define its architectonics and identify the parameters of such impact (see Figure 2). Highlighting the direct type of influence as administrative intervention of the state in the pricing process, characteristic of the DPR, one should note the priority role of the state in the formation, regulation, dynamics of price changes, and establishment of tariffs and pricing principles. This type of regulatory impact of the state on the formation of pricing policy is due to the fact that due to the economic blockade and disruption of logistical links in the Republic, there is a restructuring of goods movement; due to the devastation caused by military action, the restoration and renewal of the material and technical base is carried out; changes are also observed in the forms of organization of sales and trade management. Therefore, in such an environment, the state should integrate all management functions in the formation of pricing policy.

Figure 2 Architectonics of the system of state regulation of price policy

When regulating and, if necessary, varying prices for goods and services in the consumer market, one should focus on military-political changes and socio-economic factors and conduct constant monitoring of the situation in the consumer market. The complexity of pricing is caused by the presence of many stages, each characterized by adaptive flexibility due to constant changes in market and consumer requirements. The peculiarities of pricing in the DPR are largely dictated by the financial capabilities of the population. The analysis of the dynamics of changes in the average wage for the last three years (see Figure 3) indicates its annual increase: in 2020 – by 11.7% compared to 2019, and in 2021 – by 16.1% compared to 2020.

Figure 3 Dynamics of change in average wages in the Donetsk People's Republic (in rubles).
Compiled from the source: [18]

At the same time, the discrepancy between the growth rate of wages and the growth rate of prices should be noted. The analysis of the dynamics of price changes for the period under study showed that the price growth rate for basic foodstuffs significantly exceeded the rate of increase in average wages (see Figure 4).

For example, the price increased in 2020 compared to 2019 for such food products: “bortsch set” (potatoes, cabbage, beets, carrots, onions) – by 54%, vegetable oil – by 65.96%, bread – by 16.58%; chicken eggs – by 13.72%; poultry meat – by 8.43%; milk – by 1.94%. In 2021, the price of the following products increased: “bortsch set” – by 28.4%; poultry meat – by 44.58%; cooked sausages – by 14.91%; flour – by 30.92%; pasta – by 9.58%.

Pricing for these goods is regulated by setting marginal wholesale, marginal trade, and maximum marginal mark-ups.

Figure 4 Dynamics of prices for basic food products in the Donetsk People's Republic (in rubles/kg)

The determinant of the pricing policy of the DPR is the state of the consumer market of goods and services, the results of the assessment of which show the satisfaction of consumers' demands, breadth and depth of the range of goods, accessibility of purchase, compliance of goods with quality standards, compliance with sanitary and hygienic norms, creation of conditions for the realization of products by domestic producers, etc.

Considering the features of pricing policy at the enterprise level, it should be noted that its formation is influenced not only by external but also by internal factors, namely: the mission and purpose of the enterprise, its basic development strategy, strategic and tactical objectives, market share and competitive position in the industry market; financial status. The combination of the degree of expression of these factors determines the enterprise's active or passive pricing policy. Active pricing policy is characterized by the ability of the enterprise to respond flexibly to strategic changes and conditions in the consumer market, constantly monitor competitors' pricing policies, and use marketing tools to attract customers and increase demand and turnover.

Based on the essence of pricing policy, its most important directions and principles of formation, a scientific and methodological approach to the development of an enterprise's pricing policy is proposed, the stage scheme of which is presented in Figure 5.

Figure 5 Scientific and methodological approach to the development of an enterprise's pricing policy

In the first stage, it is required to collect information on such parameters: the definition of financial goals, taking into account the life cycle of the enterprise, analyzing customers, determining marketing strategy, cost estimation, and identification of potential competitors. Determining financial goals is conditioned by the financial condition and level of financial stability of the enterprise, considering the period of its development life cycle. Analysis of buyers and assessment of demand for goods (works, services) allows for the adjustment of, first of all, the enterprise's marketing strategy. The lower boundary of the price, depending on the value of circulation costs and the dynamics of own costs, should be less than the costs incurred in the process of production and realization of goods. The upper limit of the price is determined depending on the basic development strategy of the enterprise and the planned profit indicator. Information about competitors allows the enterprise to consider the competitive position in the industry market when forming the price.

In the second stage, the strategic analysis of competition, financial analysis, and analysis of strategic zones of enterprise management are carried out. In-depth financial analysis allows one to identify enterprise problems and assess public administration's impact.

In the third stage, the process of forming a pricing policy is carried out, which includes choosing a pricing method, determining a pricing strategy, setting the final price, and considering the mechanisms of state regulation.

To form the enterprise's pricing policy, it is necessary to calculate and evaluate the final price using one of the methods in accordance with the chosen goal. Further, the price level must be adjusted, taking into account the state pricing policy.

One of the problems complicating the implementation of the regulatory pricing policy is deep price disproportions that have developed in the Donetsk region during the years of economic and socio-political instability, provoking uncontrolled pricing and price dynamics. To solve this problem, first, it is necessary to change the forms and methods of price regulation depending on the stage of the economic cycle. Thus, for example, at the stage of economic recovery, which is characterized by an improvement in the consumer market and an increase in purchasing power, the main pricing regulators are market laws. If we assume that the stage of crisis and depression is characterized by a decline in production, deterioration of the consumer market in all its vector directions of functioning, and a decline in household incomes and, as a consequence, purchasing power, in this case, the role of the state increases, and it is advisable to focus the regulatory mechanisms of the state pricing policy on the strategy of survival.

CONCLUSION

Pricing policy research can help local companies adapt their strategies, given the DPR's unique economic and social conditions. This can lead to more efficient pricing and improved competitiveness.

The results of the analysis can be used to formulate a more effective state pricing policy aiming to stabilize the economy, fight inflation, and support the population.

Given the unstable political and economic situation in the region, analyzing the impact of external factors (e.g., sanctions, international trade) on the pricing policy can be an important area for further research.

Studying the factors that influence the pricing policy can help companies understand changes in consumer preferences and behavior, allowing them to respond more effectively to these changes.

The research may lead to the creation of new economic models that consider the specifics of the DPR and can be applied to forecast price changes in the future.

A promising direction may be comparing the DPR's pricing policy with that of other regions. This will allow for the identification of unique features and general trends and the suggestion of best practices.

The study results can be used to develop training courses and programs to educate students and specialists in economics and management.

The analysis of the pricing policy can also address social aspects, such as the impact of prices on the population's living standards, which can be important for the development of social programs and initiatives.

Thus, analyzing the factors influencing the pricing policy in the DPR has significant potential for further research and practical application.

REFERENCES

1. Bjørner, T. B., Hansen, J. V., & Jakobsen, A. F. (2021). Price cap regulation and water quality. *Journal of Regulatory Economics*, 60, 95–116. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11149-021-09439-y>
2. Ghandour, Z., & Straume, O. R. (2022). Optimal funding coverage in a mixed oligopoly with quality competition and price regulation. *Journal of Economics*, 136, 201–225. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00712-022-00778-8>
3. Chakraborti, R., & Roberts, G. (2021). Learning to Hoard: The Effects of Preexisting and Surprise Price-Gouging Regulation During the COVID-19 Pandemic. *Journal of Consumer Policy*, 44, 507–529. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10603-021-09493-1>
4. Grigsby-Duffy, L., Cameron, A. J., & Backholer, K. et al. (2022). Food industry perspectives on potential policies targeting unhealthy food and beverage price promotions in Australian supermarkets. *BMC Public Health*, 22, 1423. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12889-022-13812-7>
5. Arteaga, J. C., & Flores, D. (2022). Price Regulation and Fraud—with Special Emphasis on Gasoline Retailing. *Review of Industrial Organization*, 60, 175–192. (2022). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11151-021-09840-z>
6. Xu, H., Pan, X., & Song, M. et al. (2022). How do energy prices affect economic environment under different price regulation policies? *Environmental Science and Pollution Research*, 29, 18460–18471. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11356-021-17043-y>
7. Roeger, W., & Welfens, P. J. J. (2022). Gas price caps and electricity production effects in the context of the Russo-Ukrainian War: modeling and new policy reforms. *International Economics and Economic Policy*, 19, 645–673. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10368-022-00552-7>
8. Selvaraj, S., Farooqui, H. H., & Mehta, A. et al. (2022). Evaluating the impact of price regulation (Drug Price Control Order 2013) on antibiotic sales in India: a quasi-experimental analysis, 2008–2018. *Journal of Pharmaceutical Policy and Practice*, 15,

68. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40545-022-00466-4>
9. Rand, L. Z., & Kesselheim, A. S. (2022). Getting the Price Right: Lessons for Medicare Price Negotiation from Peer Countries. *PharmacoEconomics*, 40, 1131–1142. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40273-022-01195-x>
10. Chen, J., & Miraldo, M. (2022). The impact of hospital price and quality transparency tools on healthcare spending: a systematic review. *Health Economics Review*, 12, 62. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s13561-022-00409-4>
11. Shaikh, M., Del Giudice, P., & Kourouklis, D. (2021). Revisiting the Relationship Between Price Regulation and Pharmaceutical R&D Investment. *Applied Health Economics and Health Policy*, 19, 217–229. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40258-020-00601-9>
12. Weerahewa, J. (2022). Partial Equilibrium Analysis of Agricultural Price Policies. In: Weerahewa, J., Jacque, A. (eds) *Agricultural Policy Analysis*. Springer, Singapore. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-981-16-3284-6_11
13. Zafar, S., Aarif, M. & Tarique, M. (2023). Input subsidies, public investments and agricultural productivity in India. *Future Business Journal*, 9, 54. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s43093-023-00232-1>
14. Staritz, C., Truster, B., & Grumiller, J. et al. (2023). Price-Setting Power in Global Value Chains: The Cases of Price Stabilisation in the Cocoa Sectors in Côte d'Ivoire and Ghana. *The European Journal of Development Research*, 35, 840–868. <https://doi.org/10.1057/s41287-022-00543-z>
15. Jain, T., Hazra, J., & Cheng, T. C. E. (2023). Analysis of upstream pricing regulation and contract structure in an agriculture supply chain. *Annals of Operations Research*, 320, 85–122. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10479-022-04902-1>
16. Stelmakhova, N.V. (2021). Sphere of trade of the Donetsk People's Republic: problems, directions of development. *Bulletin of the Institute of Economic Research*, 2 (22), 49-57.
17. Resolution of the Council of Ministers of the DNR “On the Procedure for Introducing Temporary State Administrations at Enterprises, Institutions and Other Facilities” No. 35-8-41 of 26.09.2014. Available at: <https://pravdnr.ru/npa/postanovlenie-soveta-ministrov-doneczkoj-narodnoj-respubliki-ot-26-sentyabrya-2014-g-%E2%84%96-35-8-o-poryadke-vvedeniya-vremennyh-gosudarstvennyh-administracij-na-predpriyatiyah-i-v-uchrezhde/> (accessed 12.03.2023)
18. Results of the work of the Ministry of Industry and Trade for 2020. Available at: <https://mpt.gov-dpr.ru/news/1596-itogi-2020-goda.html> (accessed 13.03.2023)

INFORMATION ABOUT THE AUTHORS

Lyubov I. Donets (Donetsk Republic, Donetsk) – Professor, Dr. Sci. (Econ.), Professor of the Department of Enterprise Economics and Personnel Management. Donetsk National University of Economics and Trade named after Mikhail Tugan-Baranovsky.

Svetlana M. Barantseva (Donetsk Republic, Donetsk) – Associate Professor, Cand. Sci. (Econ.), Associate Professor of the Department of Enterprise Economics and Personnel Management. Donetsk National University of Economics and Trade named after Mikhail Tugan-Baranovsky.

Available:

Received: Dec 17, 2022 | **Accepted:** Mar 10, 2023 | **Published:** Jun 1, 2023

Editor: Gerardo Reyes Guzman, PhD in Economics. Universidad IEXE, MEXICO

Copyright: © 2023 Donets, L., Barantseva, S. This is an open access article distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License, which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original author and source are credited.

Competing interests: The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.